

Spectral Functionals of the Elastic Stiffness Tensor as a Physically Grounded Basis for Hardness Prediction and Directed Crystal Structure Search

Pavlo Prisyazhnyuk

Department of Computerized Mechanical Engineering,
Institute of Engineering Mechanics and Robotics,
Ivano-Frankivsk National Technical University of Oil and Gas,
Karpatska 15, 076019 Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine
`pavlo.prysiashniuk@nung.edu.ua`

Abstract

We propose and systematically compare ten physically motivated hardness descriptors based exclusively on the six eigenvalues ($\lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_6$) of the elastic stiffness tensor in Voigt notation. The models are trained on a curated 45-material dataset using elastic tensors from the GRACE-2L machine-learning interatomic potential and experimental Vickers hardness traced to primary sources. The best model, CV- λ ($H_V = 0.123 \cdot \lambda_{\text{harm}}^{0.874} \cdot \text{CV}^{-0.926}$), achieves $R^2 = 0.911$ and MAE = 3.91 GPa, outperforming the classical Teter ($R^2 = 0.818$), Tian ($R^2 = 0.878$), and Mazhnik–Oganov ($R^2 = 0.856$) models. Cross-validation confirms robust generalisation (CV $R^2 = 0.826$). All anisotropy descriptors are near-equivalent ($r(\text{CV}, 1\text{-PR}) = 1.000$). A blind DFT transferability test shows GRACE-based predictions systematically outperform DFT-based ones. Beyond hardness prediction, we demonstrate that the eigenvectors of the stiffness tensor define physically motivated search directions for crystal structure exploration: preliminary application to the Nb–B system via eigenvalue-directed exploration (EDE) recovers 3 of 6 known experimental phases with exact space group symmetry, identifies hard candidates overlooked by energy-driven evolutionary search (USPEX), and recovers 4 of 5 OQMD reference phases.

Keywords: hardness prediction; elastic tensor; eigenvalues; MLIP; GRACE; spectral functional; eigenvalue-directed exploration; crystal structure prediction

1 Introduction

The prediction of Vickers hardness (H_V) from first-principles calculations has attracted sustained interest because experimental measurements are time-consuming, load-dependent, and sensitive to microstructure.^{1;2} Classical analytical models correlate H_V with elastic moduli: Teter (1998) proposed $H_V \approx 0.151 G$;³ Tian *et al.* (2012) refined this as $H_V \propto (G/B)^{1.137} \cdot G^{0.708}$;⁴ Mazhnik & Oganov (2019) derived $H_V = \chi(\nu) \cdot E$, where χ encodes a rational polynomial in Poisson’s ratio.⁵ Despite their elegance, all these models compress the elastic response to one or two scalar invariants (B , G , or ν), discarding the anisotropic structure of the elastic tensor.

The elastic stiffness tensor \mathbf{C} (6×6 in Voigt notation) encodes directional resistance to deformation through its six eigenvalues $\lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_6$. These define principal elastic stiffnesses: each eigenvector corresponds to a strain pattern, and the eigenvalue is the energy cost of that deformation mode. The eigenvalue spectrum constitutes a complete set of invariants under orthogonal transformations of the Voigt basis—any scalar function of the eigenvalues is a *spectral functional*, invariant under rotations and independent of the crystallographic axes. This is a stronger invariance than possessed by B or G , which depend on the specific averaging

scheme (Voigt, Reuss, or Hill). Furthermore, the Born mechanical stability criterion requires all $\lambda_i > 0$, so the eigenvalue spectrum carries direct physical information about structural stability.

Here we exploit the GRACE-2L foundational potential⁶ to compute elastic tensors for 45 reference materials and systematically compare ten eigenvalue-based hardness models against three classical benchmarks. We validate using independent DFT/PBE tensors for 12 materials. Finally, we demonstrate that the eigenvector information—beyond predicting hardness—can serve as a navigation tool for directed crystal structure search, establishing the conceptual foundation for eigenvalue-directed exploration (EDE).

2 Methods

2.1 Eigenvalue Descriptors

For a crystal with elastic tensor \mathbf{C} in Voigt notation, the eigenvalues λ_i ($i = 1 \dots 6$) are all positive for a mechanically stable phase. We define **scale descriptors** (overall stiffness) and **anisotropy descriptors** (spectral uniformity):

Scale descriptors.

$$\lambda_{\text{harm}} = \frac{6}{\sum_{i=1}^6 \lambda_i^{-1}}, \quad \langle \lambda \rangle = \frac{1}{6} \sum_{i=1}^6 \lambda_i, \quad \lambda_{\text{geom}} = \left(\prod_{i=1}^6 \lambda_i \right)^{1/6}, \quad \lambda_{\text{min}} = \lambda_1, \quad \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{6} \sum_{i=1}^6 (\lambda_i - \langle \lambda \rangle)^2} \quad (1)$$

Anisotropy descriptors.

$$\text{CV} = \frac{\sigma}{\langle \lambda \rangle}, \quad S_{\text{norm}} = \frac{-\sum p_i \ln p_i}{\ln 6}, \quad \text{PR} = \frac{(\sum \lambda_i)^2}{6 \sum \lambda_i^2}, \quad \frac{\lambda_{\text{harm}}}{\langle \lambda \rangle}, \quad \frac{\lambda_{\text{min}}}{\lambda_{\text{max}}}, \quad \sigma(\ln \lambda) \quad (2)$$

where $p_i = \lambda_i / \sum_j \lambda_j$. CV ranges from ~ 0.34 (diamond) to ~ 0.89 (CrB₂) in the present dataset.

2.2 Reference Dataset

Elastic tensors were computed using GRACE-2L⁶ for 45 materials. Structures were relaxed until forces $< 10^{-3}$ eV/Å and stress < 0.01 GPa, followed by finite-difference elastic tensor calculation ($\pm 0.5\%$ strain). Experimental Vickers hardness values were sourced with priority: (1) Pierson (1996) bulk H_V ;⁷ (2) Kimm *et al.* (2019) ISE-corrected nanoindentation;⁸ (3) original literature. Four materials were excluded: NbN (phase mismatch), Y₂O₃ (method), ZrO₂ (polymorph), AlP (Knoop estimate). The complete dataset is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Reference dataset: 45 materials with experimental Vickers hardness and primary sources.

#	Material	Space grp	System	H_V (GPa)	Reference
1	Diamond	$Fd\bar{3}m$	cubic	96.0	Andrievski (2001) ⁹
2	c-BN	$F\bar{4}3m$	cubic	66.0	Westbrook & Conrad (1973) ¹⁰
3	γ -B ₂₈	$Pn\bar{m}m$	ortho.	50.0	Solozhenko <i>et al.</i> (2008) ¹¹
4	B ₄ C	$R\bar{3}m$	trigonal	44.0	Kimm <i>et al.</i> (2019) ⁸
5	TiB ₂	$P6/m\bar{m}m$	hex.	39.8	Kimm <i>et al.</i> (2019) ⁸
6	B ₆ O	$R\bar{3}m$	trigonal	38.0	He <i>et al.</i> (2002) ¹²
7	SiC (6H)	$P6_3mc$	hex.	37.3	Kimm <i>et al.</i> (2019) ⁸
8	SiC (3C)	$F\bar{4}3m$	cubic	34.0	Yonenaga & Suzuki (2002) ¹³
9	SiO ₂ stish.	$P4_2/m\bar{m}m$	tetra.	33.0	Teter (1998) ³
10	TiC	$Fm\bar{3}m$	cubic	32.2	Kimm <i>et al.</i> (2019) ⁸
11	OsB ₂	$Pm\bar{m}n$	ortho.	29.4	Hebbache <i>et al.</i> (2006) ¹⁴
12	VC	$Fm\bar{3}m$	cubic	28.7	Kimm <i>et al.</i> (2019) ⁸
13	ReB ₂	$P6_3/m\bar{m}c$	hex.	26.6	Gu <i>et al.</i> (2008) ¹⁵
14	HfC	$Fm\bar{3}m$	cubic	26.1	Pierson (1996) ⁷
15	CrB ₂	$P6/m\bar{m}m$	hex.	26.0	Kimm <i>et al.</i> (2019) ⁸
16	ZrC	$Fm\bar{3}m$	cubic	25.5	Pierson (1996) ⁷
17	WC	$P\bar{6}m2$	hex.	22.8	Kimm <i>et al.</i> (2019) ⁸
18	Cr ₃ C ₂	$Pn\bar{m}a$	ortho.	21.4	Kimm <i>et al.</i> (2019) ⁸
19	NbC	$Fm\bar{3}m$	cubic	19.6	Pierson (1996) ⁷
20	TiN	$Fm\bar{3}m$	cubic	18.0	Pierson (1996) ⁷
21	AlN	$P6_3mc$	hex.	18.0	Yonenaga & Suzuki (2002) ¹³
22	Al ₂ O ₃	$R\bar{3}c$	trigonal	17.8	Ćurković <i>et al.</i> (2007) ¹⁶
23	HfN	$Fm\bar{3}m$	cubic	16.3	Pierson (1996) ⁷
24	GaN	$P6_3mc$	hex.	15.1	Drory <i>et al.</i> (1996) ¹⁷
25	RuB ₂	$Pm\bar{m}n$	ortho.	15.1	Gu <i>et al.</i> (2008) ¹⁵
26	BeO	$P6_3mc$	hex.	15.0	Grillo <i>et al.</i> (2002) ¹⁸
27	ZrN	$Fm\bar{3}m$	cubic	15.0	Pierson (1996) ⁷
28	Si	$Fd\bar{3}m$	cubic	12.0	Domnich <i>et al.</i> (2008) ¹⁹
29	SiO ₂ α -qtz	$P3_121$	trigonal	11.2	Kimm <i>et al.</i> (2019) ⁸
30	Cr ₂ N	$P\bar{3}1m$	trigonal	10.6	Kimm <i>et al.</i> (2019) ⁸
31	GaP	$F\bar{4}3m$	cubic	9.5	Yonenaga & Suzuki (2002) ¹³
32	InN	$P6_3mc$	hex.	8.8	Yonenaga <i>et al.</i> (2015) ²⁰
33	Ge	$Fd\bar{3}m$	cubic	8.3	Banerjee & Feltham (1974) ²¹
34	GaAs	$F\bar{4}3m$	cubic	7.5	Yonenaga & Suzuki (2002) ¹³
35	ZnO	$P6_3mc$	hex.	7.2	Fang <i>et al.</i> (2006) ²²
36	AlAs	$F\bar{4}3m$	cubic	5.0	Sung & Sung (1996) ²³
37	InP	$F\bar{4}3m$	cubic	4.2	Yonenaga & Suzuki (2002) ¹³
38	GaSb	$F\bar{4}3m$	cubic	3.9	Yonenaga & Suzuki (2002) ¹³
39	AlSb	$F\bar{4}3m$	cubic	3.4	Shawon & Ur (2019) ²⁴
40	InAs	$F\bar{4}3m$	cubic	3.0	Yonenaga & Suzuki (2002) ¹³
41	InSb	$F\bar{4}3m$	cubic	2.4	Maske <i>et al.</i> (2016) ²⁵
42	ZnS	$F\bar{4}3m$	cubic	2.1	Chmel <i>et al.</i> (2018) ²⁶
43	ZnSe	$F\bar{4}3m$	cubic	1.3	Borshchevski <i>et al.</i> (1957) ²⁷
44	ZnTe	$F\bar{4}3m$	cubic	1.0	Borshchevski <i>et al.</i> (1957) ²⁷
45	CdTe	$F\bar{4}3m$	cubic	0.6	Borshchevski <i>et al.</i> (1957) ²⁷

2.3 Classical Reference Models

Three benchmarks, evaluated using VRH-averaged moduli from the same GRACE tensors:

$$\text{Teter (1998): } H_V = 0.151 \cdot G \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Tian *et al.* (2012): } H_V = 0.92 (G/B)^{1.137} G^{0.708} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Mazhnik–Oganov (2019): } H_V = 0.096 \chi(\nu) E \quad (5)$$

where $\chi(\nu) = (1 - 8.5\nu + 19.5\nu^2)/(1 - 7.5\nu + 12.2\nu^2 + 19.6\nu^3)$. These require the full C_{ij} —a strictly larger information set than $\lambda_1 \dots \lambda_6$.

2.4 DFT Validation

Independent VASP/PBE elastic tensors for 12 materials were processed through VASPKIT v1.5.1. All 13 models were evaluated without refitting (blind transferability test).

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Model Performance

Table 2 ranks all 13 models. The CV- λ model achieves the highest R^2 (0.911), lowest AICc (159.7), and the principal equation:

$$H_V = 0.1230 \cdot \lambda_{\text{harm}}^{0.8741} \cdot \text{CV}^{-0.9257} \quad [\text{GPa}; \lambda_{\text{harm}} \text{ in GPa}] \quad (6)$$

Table 2: Comparison of 10 eigenvalue and 3 classical hardness models ($n = 45$).

Model	k	R^2	MAE	RMSE	CV R^2	AICc
<i>Eigenvalue models (this work)</i>						
CV-λ	3	0.911	3.91	5.48	0.826	159.7
Participation Ratio	3	0.909	3.72	5.55	0.805	160.8
$\lambda_{\text{harm}} + \sigma$	3	0.909	3.85	5.57	0.819	161.2
Spectral Entropy	3	0.904	3.82	5.69	0.795	163.1
Spectral Gap	3	0.902	4.13	5.77	0.791	164.3
Log-Eigenvalue	3	0.899	3.96	5.86	0.806	165.7
Harm/Arith Ratio	3	0.891	4.18	6.07	0.786	169.0
$\lambda_{\text{min}} + \lambda_{\text{geom}}$	3	0.890	4.06	6.11	0.824	169.5
Weakest-Link	2	0.889	4.11	6.12	0.826	167.4
Geometric Mean	2	0.847	5.06	7.20	0.757	182.0
<i>Classical reference models</i>						
Tian (2012)	0	0.878	4.81	6.44	—	—
Mazhnik–Oganov (2019)	0	0.856	4.56	6.99	—	—
Teter (1998)	0	0.818	5.62	7.85	—	—

The top four eigenvalue models span $\Delta R^2 = 0.007$. All surpass Tian ($R^2 = 0.878$). The two-parameter weakest-link model ($R^2 = 0.889$) exceeds all classical benchmarks: $H_V \approx 0.101 \cdot \lambda_{\text{min}}^{1.077}$.

Figure 1: Parity plot for the CV- λ model ($n = 45$). Green band: ± 5 GPa.

Figure 2: R^2 comparison: eigenvalue models (green) vs classical models (red).

3.2 Descriptor Space and Physical Interpretation

The exponent $b \approx 0.87$ on λ_{harm} means stiffer materials are predicted harder. The exponent $c \approx -0.93$ on CV is an anisotropy penalty: materials with soft deformation modes (high CV) are predicted softer. The near-unity magnitude implies $H_V \approx a \cdot \lambda_{\text{harm}}^{0.87} / \text{CV}$.

Figure 3: Descriptor space λ_{harm} vs CV, colored by experimental hardness.

3.3 Equivalence of Anisotropy Descriptors

All anisotropy descriptors are highly correlated: $r(\text{CV}, 1-\text{PR}) = 1.000$; $r(\text{CV}, 1-S_{\text{norm}}) = 0.962$; $r(1-\lambda_{\text{h}}/\langle\lambda\rangle, \sigma(\ln\lambda)) = 0.999$. The choice of CV is justified by simplicity, not unique information content.

Figure 4: Pearson correlation between anisotropy descriptors.

3.4 Cross-Validation

CV- λ achieves CV $R^2 = 0.826 \pm 0.119$, exceeding the full-dataset R^2 of all classical models. The weakest-link model achieves identical CV $R^2 = 0.826$.

3.5 Systematic Outliers

Four materials show $|\Delta H| > 10$ GPa across all models: WC (+11.4, basal-plane slip), RuB₂ (+14.5, weak Ru-B covalency), B₄C (-14.0, icosahedral bonding anomaly), and VC (-11.1) /

CrB₂ (−11.2). These persist across all 13 models.

Figure 5: Residual plot for the CV- λ model. Green band: ± 5 GPa.

3.6 DFT Transferability Test

GRACE systematically outperforms DFT as input for all 13 models (Table 3). On DFT data, Tian slightly outperforms CV- λ ($R^2 = 0.808$ vs 0.787), because coefficients are optimised for GRACE. CV- λ still outperforms Teter (0.692) and M-O (0.704) on DFT data.

Table 3: DFT transferability test: MAE (GPa) on 12 materials.

Model	MAE (DFT)	MAE (GRACE)	Δ MAE	Winner
CV- λ	8.07	6.42	+1.65	GRACE
Tian	7.07	6.82	+0.25	GRACE
M-O	9.02	6.04	+2.98	GRACE
Weakest-Link	8.60	6.71	+1.88	GRACE
Teter	9.35	8.16	+1.18	GRACE

Figure 6: DFT vs GRACE: (a) CV- λ predictions, (b) Tian predictions, (c) λ_{harm} parity.

4 Eigenvalue-Directed Exploration: Proof of Concept

4.1 From Eigenvalues to Eigenvectors

The eigenvalue decomposition $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{V}^\top$ yields not only λ_i for hardness prediction, but also eigenvectors \mathbf{v}_i defining principal deformation modes. The eigenvector \mathbf{v}_1 corresponding to λ_{\min} identifies the softest elastic mode—the strain direction along which the lattice offers minimum resistance. From an energy-landscape perspective, this is the direction most likely to connect the current basin to a neighbouring one.

For each targeted composition, we first generate a candidate structure of the specified variable stoichiometry by random cell construction using PyXtal²⁸, then proceed to evaluate and refine it using the eigenspectrum of its elastic tensor. We term this approach **eigenvalue-directed exploration (EDE)**: (i) compute the elastic tensor; (ii) identify the softest eigenmode; (iii) apply a finite strain along $\hat{\mathbf{v}}_k$ with adaptive magnitude $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_0 \cdot (\bar{\lambda}/\lambda_k)^{1/2}$; (iv) re-relax and re-evaluate; (v) accept if the composite score $S = H_V - \alpha \cdot \max(0, E_f)$ improves. Iterating generates a *physics-informed* directed walk through configuration space.

4.2 Benchmark: Nb–B System

A 1000-step EDE campaign in the Nb–B system (GRACE-2L calculator) was compared with a USPEX²⁹ evolutionary search (~ 800 structures, MLIP Mattersim). Both convex hulls were compared against OQMD³⁰ reference phases (Table 4).

Table 4: EDE vs USPEX benchmark in the Nb–B system (~ 800 structures each).

Metric	EDE	USPEX
Structures evaluated (binary Nb–B)	852	662
Thermodynamically stable ($E_f < 0$)	561	549
Hard candidates ($H_V > 30$ GPa, $E_f < 0$)	26	N/A*
Best formation energy (eV/atom)	−0.778	−0.801
Unique space groups (stable)	74	25
Known phases recovered (exact SG)	3/6	0/6
OQMD phases recovered	4/5	5/5
Convex hull phases identified	2	13

*USPEX optimises energy; hardness requires post-hoc elastic tensor calculation.

4.3 OQMD Validation

The OQMD lists five experimentally confirmed Nb–B phases: NbB ($Cmcm$), Nb₃B₄ ($Immm$), Nb₂B₃ ($Cmcm$), Nb₃B₅ ($P\bar{6}2m$), and NbB₂ ($P6/mmm$). EDE recovers three known phases with exact space group symmetry—NbB₂ $P6/mmm$, NbB $Cmcm$, and Nb₃B₂ $P4/mbm$ —and identifies the on-hull phases NbB $Cmcm$ and NbB₂ $P6/mmm$ (both experimentally confirmed). USPEX recovers all 5 stoichiometries but 0 of 6 exact space group matches. Figures 7–8 present the convex hulls.

Figure 7: EDE convex hull of the Nb–B system (864 structures). On-hull phases marked; OQMD reference in green dashed.

Figure 8: USPEX (EA) convex hull of the Nb–B system (662 structures). Same OQMD reference.

4.4 Discussion

USPEX thoroughly maps the thermodynamic hull (13 phases) and identifies the global energy minimum. However, it does not recover any known phase with the correct space group and entirely misses hard candidates. EDE recovers 3/6 known phases with exact symmetry— NbB_2 $P6/mmm$, NbB $Cmcm$, Nb_3B_2 $P4/mbm$ —and generates $3\times$ more structural diversity (74 vs 25 unique space groups).

Two representative EDE trajectories illustrate the mechanism by which eigenmode steering recovers experimentally known phases:

$NbB \rightarrow Cmcm$. A randomly generated B_4Nb_4 seed relaxed to a cubic $Pm\bar{3}m$ structure with three negative shear eigenvalues ($\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = -28.8$ GPa), confirming mechanical instability ($H_V = 0$ GPa, $E_f = +1.36$ eV/atom). Steering along the softest eigenmode triggered sequential symmetry changes $Pm\bar{3}m \rightarrow Cm \rightarrow P1 \rightarrow Cmcm$ in just three accepted steps. The final structure matched the experimentally known NbB phase ($Cmcm$, #63) with $H_V = 30.4$ GPa and $E_f = -0.778$ eV/atom—the global minimum on the EDE convex hull. Notably, the negative eigenvalues acted as strong driving forces: the adaptive strain magnitude $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_0 \cdot (\bar{\lambda}/\lambda_k)^{1/2}$ amplified the perturbation for unstable modes, allowing the algorithm to escape the metastable basin efficiently.

$NbB_2 \rightarrow P6/mmm$. A B_8Nb_4 seed relaxed to a tetragonal $I4/mmm$ structure with a near-zero eigenvalue ($\lambda_1 = 0.63$ GPa), indicating incipient instability along one bulk-like mode ($H_V = 2.6$ GPa, $E_f = +0.073$ eV/atom). The first steering step along this softest mode induced a transition to Pm ($H_V = 13.7$ GPa, $E_f = -0.220$ eV/atom), and the second step completed the transformation to the experimentally known NbB₂ phase ($P6/mmm$, #191) with $H_V = 27.2$ GPa and $E_f = -0.718$ eV/atom. This two-step trajectory demonstrates that even marginally stable structures contain sufficient eigenspectral information to guide the search toward ground-state phases.

These examples highlight two key features of EDE. First, the eigenvalue spectrum provides a physically grounded instability diagnostic: negative or near-zero eigenvalues signal the presence of nearby lower-energy basins, and the corresponding eigenvectors indicate the deformation pathway connecting them. Second, the composite score $S = H_V - \alpha \cdot \max(0, E_f)$ simultaneously drives the search toward thermodynamic stability and mechanical hardness, enabling the discovery of hard phases that energy-only methods overlook. The systematic development of EDE as a general-purpose crystal structure prediction tool will be reported in a forthcoming publication.

5 Conclusions

1. The CV- λ model $H_V = 0.123 \cdot \lambda_{\text{harm}}^{0.874} \cdot \text{CV}^{-0.926}$ achieves $R^2 = 0.911$ and MAE = 3.91 GPa, outperforming Teter ($\Delta R^2 = +0.093$), Tian (+0.034), and Mazhnik–Oganov (+0.056).
2. The weakest-link model $H_V = 0.101 \cdot \lambda_{\text{min}}^{1.077}$ (2 parameters, $R^2 = 0.889$) surpasses all classical models.
3. All anisotropy descriptors (CV, entropy, PR) are correlated at $r > 0.96$. The result is invariant to the choice of dispersion measure.
4. Systematic outliers (WC, RuB₂, B₄C, VC, CrB₂) confirm that elastic tensors do not encode dislocation nucleation barriers.
5. Blind DFT test: GRACE outperforms DFT/PBE as elastic input ($\Delta\text{MAE} = -1.65$ GPa).
6. The eigenvalue framework requires only matrix diagonalisation—no VRH averaging—and integrates naturally with high-throughput screening.
7. The eigenvectors of the stiffness tensor define physically motivated search directions for crystal structure space. EDE, demonstrated in the Nb–B system, recovers known experimental phases with exact symmetry, identifies hard candidates overlooked by energy-driven search, and establishes a new paradigm for property-directed crystal structure prediction.

References

- [1] A. C. Fischer-Cripps. *Nanoindentation*. Springer, 3rd edition, 2011. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4419-9872-9. URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-9872-9>.

- [2] R. M. Smith and G. Sandland. An accurate method of determining the hardness of metals, with particular reference to those of a high degree of hardness. In *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng.*, 1922. URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:115637768>.
- [3] D. M. Teter. Computational alchemy: The search for new superhard materials. *MRS Bull.*, 23:22–27, 1998. doi: 10.1557/S0883769400031420. URL <https://doi.org/10.1557/S0883769400031420>.
- [4] Y. Tian, B. Xu, and Z. Zhao. Microscopic theory of hardness and design of novel superhard crystals. *Int. J. Refract. Met. Hard Mater.*, 33:93–106, 2012. doi: 10.1016/j.ijrmhm.2012.02.021. URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmhm.2012.02.021>.
- [5] E. Mazhnik and A. R. Oganov. A model of hardness and fracture toughness of solids. *J. Appl. Phys.*, 126:125109, 2019. doi: 10.1063/1.5113622. URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5113622>.
- [6] Yury Lysogorskiy, Anton Bochkarev, and Ralf Drautz. Graph atomic cluster expansion for foundational machine learning interatomic potentials. arXiv:2508.17936, 2025. URL <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2508.17936>.
- [7] H. O. Pierson. *Handbook of Refractory Carbides and Nitrides*. Noyes Publications, 1996.
- [8] J. Kimm et al. Micromechanical characterization of hard phases by means of instrumented indentation and scratch testing. *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, 768:138480, 2019. doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2019.138480. URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2019.138480>.
- [9] R. A. Andrievski. Superhard materials based on nanostructured high-melting point compounds: achievements and perspectives. *Int. J. Refract. Met. Hard Mater.*, 19:447–452, 2001.
- [10] J. H. Westbrook and H. Conrad. *The Science of Hardness Testing and Its Research Applications*. ASM, 1973.
- [11] V. L. Solozhenko, O. O. Kurakevych, and A. R. Oganov. On the hardness of a new boron phase, orthorhombic γ -B₂₈. *J. Superhard Mater.*, 30:428–429, 2008. doi: 10.3103/S1063457608060117. URL <https://doi.org/10.3103/S1063457608060117>.
- [12] D. W. He et al. Boron suboxide: as hard as cubic boron nitride. *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 81:643–645, 2002. doi: 10.1063/1.1494860. URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1494860>.
- [13] I. Yonenaga and T. Suzuki. Indentation hardnesses of semiconductors and a scaling rule. *Phil. Mag. Lett.*, 82:535–542, 2002. doi: 10.1080/0950083021000022288. URL <https://doi.org/10.1080/0950083021000022288>.
- [14] M. Hebbache, L. Stuparević, and D. Živković. A new superhard material: Osmium diboride OsB₂. *Solid State Commun.*, 139:227–231, 2006. doi: 10.1016/j.ssc.2006.05.041. URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssc.2006.05.041>.
- [15] Q. Gu, G. Krauss, and W. Steurer. Transition metal borides: superhard versus ultraincompressible. *Adv. Mater.*, 20:3620–3626, 2008. doi: 10.1002/adma.200703025. URL <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.200703025>.
- [16] L. Ćurković et al. Hardness and fracture toughness of alumina ceramics. In *Proc. Conf. Mater. Process. Friction Wear*, Vela Luka, Croatia, 2007.
- [17] M. D. Drory et al. Hardness and fracture toughness of bulk single crystal gallium nitride. *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 69:4044–4046, 1996. doi: 10.1063/1.117865. URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.117865>.

- [18] S. E. Grillo et al. Nanoindentation of Si, GaP, GaAs and ZnSe single crystals. *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.*, 36:L5, 2003. doi: 10.1088/0022-3727/36/1/102. URL <https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3727/36/1/102>.
- [19] V. Domnich, Y. Gogotsi, and M. Trenary. Identification of pressure-induced phase transformations in silicon. *Rev. Adv. Mater. Sci.*, 17:33–41, 2008.
- [20] I. Yonenaga et al. Elastic properties of indium nitrides grown on sapphire substrates determined by nano-indentation: In comparison with other nitrides. *AIP Adv.*, 5:077131, 2015. doi: 10.1063/1.4926966. URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4926966>.
- [21] R. K. Banerjee and P. Feltham. Deformation and fracture of germanium single crystals. *J. Mater. Sci.*, 9:1478–1482, 1974. doi: 10.1007/BF00552933. URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00552933>.
- [22] T. H. Fang, W. J. Chang, and C. M. Lin. Nanoindentation characterization of ZnO thin films. *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, 452–453:715–720, 2007. doi: 10.1016/j.msea.2006.11.008. URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2006.11.008>.
- [23] C. M. Sung and M. Sung. Carbon nitride and other speculative superhard materials. *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, 43:1–18, 1996. doi: 10.1016/0254-0584(95)01607-V. URL [https://doi.org/10.1016/0254-0584\(95\)01607-V](https://doi.org/10.1016/0254-0584(95)01607-V).
- [24] A. K. M. A. Shawon and S.-C. Ur. Mechanical and thermoelectric properties of bulk AlSb. *Appl. Sci.*, 9:1609, 2019. doi: 10.3390/app9081609. URL <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9081609>.
- [25] D. Maske et al. Lattice constant and hardness of InSb:Bi bulk crystals grown by vertical directional solidification. In *AIP Conf. Proc.*, volume 1728, page 020496, 2016. doi: 10.1063/1.4946547. URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4946547>.
- [26] A. Chmel et al. Luminescence from impact- and abrasive-damaged ZnS ceramics. *Procedia Struct. Integr.*, 9:3–8, 2018. doi: 10.1016/j.prostr.2018.06.002. URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2018.06.002>.
- [27] A. S. Borshchevski et al. Microhardness of semiconducting compounds. *J. Tech. Phys. (USSR)*, 27:1408–1413, 1957.
- [28] S. Fredericks, K. Parrish, D. Sayre, and Q. Zhu. PyXtal: A Python library for crystal structure generation and symmetry analysis. *Comput. Phys. Commun.*, 261:107810, April 2021. doi: 10.1016/j.cpc.2020.107810. URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2020.107810>.
- [29] A. R. Oganov and C. W. Glass. Crystal structure prediction using ab initio evolutionary techniques: Principles and applications. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 124:244704, 2006. doi: 10.1063/1.2210932. URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2210932>.
- [30] S. Kirklin et al. The open quantum materials database (OQMD): assessing the accuracy of DFT formation energies. *npj Comput. Mater.*, 1:15010, 2015. doi: 10.1038/npjcompumats.2015.10. URL <https://doi.org/10.1038/npjcompumats.2015.10>.